

Semiconductor IC Package Sidewall Augmentation for Package Chip-out Mitigation

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Abstract—The paper presents an improvement on the semiconductor integrated circuit (IC) package’s sidewalls for mitigation of package chip-out and for prolonging the singulation blade life.

Keywords— Chip-out; sidewall; semiconductor package; blade life.

I. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

- Package chip-out was evident on Device A with measurement greater than the specification (or specs) limit of 125µm

Fig. 1. Device A chip-out.

Fig. 2. Package chip-out specification.

- Parameter optimization, blade selection and evaluation, and ensuring planarity and calibration can help mitigate the package chip-out, still chip-out cannot be totally eliminated due to the degradation of the singulation blade

Fig. 3. Types of mechanical saw package singulation.

II. DESIGN SOLUTION

- The rejection caused by out-of-specs topside package chip-out could be eliminated through provision of indented design on the actual structure of the semiconductor integrated circuit (IC) package

Fig. 4. Semiconductor IC package with indented sidewalls.

- The indented sidewalls are realized during mold encapsulation using modified and specialized design of the mold chase
- The lower part of the package without the indented design is the only part to be cut or sawn using mechanical blades during singulation process – prolonging the blade life